

MANAGEMENT OF STRATEGIC ISSUES IN ISLAMIC UNIVERSITIES: A SWOT ANALYSIS APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The management of strategic issues in Islamic tertiary institutions, both public and private, has not yet been able to achieve its target, which is to become a leading, superior, competitive, and globally competitive Islamic religious university. Meanwhile, the demands of society are increasingly critical in choosing a quality university. The approach used to overcome these problems is to use a SWOT analysis. UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan became the object of this research. This research is a qualitative descriptive. Data collection techniques are carried out by organizing, strengthening, processing, and classifying systematically. It uses free guided interview techniques, in-depth observation, and comprehensive documentation. The results of this study found that the SWOT analysis of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan in the management of strategic issues is made based on four components, namely the needs of the community, the needs of national development, the development of science and technology and the arts, as well as the potential for growth in the number of students. The findings of this study also show that external factors are positive but internal factors are negative. This position shows that the opportunities faced are still greater than the existing threats. On the internal side, the strengths or advantages they have are relatively smaller than their weaknesses. Thus, the policy direction that must be chosen is to maintain the role of UIN K.H. The current Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is aggressively or selectively in carrying out the work program. In this condition, the basic policy direction that must be implemented is to maintain the stability of existing and ongoing activities. The direction of its development strategy in managing strategic issues is carried out based on three main targets, namely to become a good university governance, competitive advantage university, and global recognition university.

Keywords: planning, management, issues, strategic, higher education, and SWOT.

INTRODUCTION

Management of strategic issues is very urgent in higher education (Bromiley & Rau, 2022), because it is used as a reference by the academic community and university residents in the UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan in carrying out the duties of the tri dharma of higher education. With the hope that it can also be useful for stakeholders. Therefore, its existence is very useful for various parties who want to know the ins and outs of strategic policies set at the internal and external levels, so that they can be used as standards for managing the managerial performance of higher education institutions in an accountable manner (Zhao, 2022).

UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has a fairly heavy task, namely improving infrastructure or facilities, system development, and the quality of human resources, as well as making a real contribution to the development of science and society, both at local, national and international levels. In this context, the development of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan needs a more structured and measurable management of strategic issues, both in terms of system development, organizational structure, and human resource management that

are more rational, cultural, and professional work ethic as well as a transparent and accountable financial management system (Schaedler et al., 2022).

Management of strategic issues at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is part of a medium-term plan that is aligned with the mandate of the 2020-2024 National Medium-Term Development Plan to the Ministry of Religion, namely increasing quality and competitive human resources as well as a mental revolution and cultural development which is translated into the Priority Program and Development Goals in the Religion Sector. 2020-2024. The priority programs of the Ministry of Religion include: Increasing Equitable Quality Education Services, Increasing Productivity and Competitiveness, Mental Revolution and Pancasila Ideology Development, Strengthening Religious Moderation, and Increasing Literacy, Innovation, and Creativity (Alawattage & Wickramasinghe, 2022). The development goals in the field of Religion 2020-2024 are improving the quality of religious piety, strengthening moderation and religious harmony, providing fair and equitable religious services, increasing institutional empowerment and economic resources of the people, expanding access to public education with religious characteristics, religious education and religious, Improving the quality of management and the quality of general education characterized by religion, religious and religious education, and Improving the quality of effective and accountable governance (Stavros et al., 2022).

The presence of the management of these strategic issues becomes an inspiring blue print for every service of the tri dharma of higher education within the UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, so it will be more qualified. Its existence is one of the barometers to measure the performance of higher education institutions (Menz & Scheef, 2014). This strategic plan can also encourage better institutional quality and reputation. Thus, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can be a role model for those who strive to develop the tri dharma of higher education in a plenary manner. Thus, this strategic issue management document can be an entry point for the implementation of the vision of “The realization of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan as a leading and competitive university at the global level in the development of harmonization of science and religion towards a pious, intelligent, superior, and moderate society”.

State Islamic Religious Universities are an important and inseparable part of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia under the Directorate of Islamic Education. UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is one of the State Islamic Religious Universities which was officially inaugurated through Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 73 of 2016. UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is tasked with “organizing academic education in a certain number of science and/or technology clusters”, as stated in the Minister of Religion Regulation Number 47 of 2016 concerning Organization and Governance. So that in determining the direction and policies of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan must be in line with the Ministry of Religion, especially the Directorate of Islamic Education.

In accordance with the Master Plan for the Development of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, the milestone of the first stage is Good University Governance. So that for a period of 4 years running, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has implemented the

management of strategic issues with full of challenges and dynamics towards Good University Governance.

In order to achieve the above vision, mission and goals, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan always tries to improve governance in an accountable manner. UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has determined the Long-Term Strategy in the form of the formulation of the Master Plan for development until 2036, which is divided into four stages of milestones. The first stage is Good University Governance, the second stage is University's Performance Improvement, the third stage is Competitive Advantages University, and the fourth stage is Global Recognition University. Currently, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is focusing on the first phase of the achievement target, realizing the principles of Good University Governance. At this stage, the strategic plan further strengthens the scientific base of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan who has an Indonesian perspective towards an Islamic Religious College that excels at the national level, by creating a conducive academic atmosphere and sound management or Good University Governance.

Behind the availability and socialization of the vision, mission, goals, and strategic plans of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan does not mean that there are no potential problems. Based on the expression of the vision and mission, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan aspires to become a leading Islamic religious university, known as a superior university in Indonesia, competitive and able to compete academically and non-academicly with the target of being ranked in the top ten among Islamic religious universities. Meanwhile, society is now increasingly critical in choosing a quality university (Johnson, 1988). One of the indicators of a quality university is the achievement of accreditation with the title of Excellence (Korshunova & Beresneva, 2021). Meanwhile, a university will be able to obtain the title of Excellence if it is able to exceed the national standard (Chen et al., 2021). While the vision of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan only targets the predicate of excellence at the Indonesian level.

At this time UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan consolidated the formulation of the management of strategic issues as well as adjustments to the strategic plan of the Ministry of Religion which was derived from the vision and mission of the President of the Republic of Indonesia which was most recent or current. More specifically, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has a mandate to develop sustainable management of strategic issues in accordance with that of the Directorate of Islamic Education, Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. Furthermore, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan in managing strategic issues needs to analysis potential and problems as logical and academic arguments. The approach used to overcome these problems is to use a SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) (Westhues et al., 2001).

Planning is the first stage in any activity including planning for the management of strategic issues at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. This stage determines an overall series or framework. If this plan is successful then it is the same as planning for success, and vice versa if it fails in planning it is the same as planning for failure (Das, 2019). So that the analysis tool in planning is also a determining part in the success of planning.

One of the basic analytical tools in planning is to use the SWOT method (Khalid et al., 2017). The SWOT method analysis internal strengths and weaknesses as well as external analysis of opportunities and threats (Satria & Shahbana, 2020). SWOT is a simple way to estimate the best way to execute a strategy (Tools, 2020). The implementation of SWOT is very dependent on the situation and conditions, both internal and external conditions (Lestari & Saidah, 2019). In order to achieve maximum results in the SWOT analysis, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has been able to summarize the various indications used to calculate the SWOT analysis itself, as will be explained in the results of this study.

SWOT analysis works by sorting out the things that affect the four SWOT factors, then applying them to a SWOT matrix image (Nigel & William, 1989). In this matrix, it can be compared how strengths are able to take advantage of existing opportunities, how to overcome weaknesses that prevent advantages from existing opportunities, then how strengths are able to deal with existing threats, and how to overcome weaknesses that can make threats real or create a new threat (Astika & Suharyo, 2021).

The main objective of the SWOT analysis is to optimize the strength of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan and minimize personal weaknesses, as well as take advantage of opportunities that arise and overcome threats that come (Taherdoost, 2021). In the world of Islamic universities, changes in conditions and situations will often be encountered. These changes must be addressed by analysing SWOT so that the education and learning process that is carried out can survive well (Schooley, 2019).

Doing a SWOT analysis is not easy (Srinivas, 2019). Many Islamic universities use the services of consultants to conduct a SWOT analysis. However, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can do it himself objectively.

In addition to being used by Islamic universities, the SWOT analysis model is currently widely used to analysis the situation and find out the weaknesses and advantages of companies in general and especially in the field of marketing in the face of very tight global competition, as several researchs (Valentin, 2001; Maulina, 2018; Steer et al., 2019; Srinivas, 2019; Hastutik & Novitaningtyas, 2021; Benzaghta et al., 2021; Stefan et al., 2021; Mello et al., 2022; Citra Birru et al., 2022), which found that the results of the study obtained information about the company and with this information the company would be able to plan the right strategy to win the competition.

Based on the above background, research on the management of strategic issues in Islamic universities, especially at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, using a SWOT analysis approach is still very relevant to be studied in depth.

Problems and Goals

The problem of this research is UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan still has potential problems in managing strategic issues. UIN K.H. So far, Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has not been able to reach his target, which is to be ranked in the top ten among Islamic religious

universities in Indonesia. The goal of this study is to describe the management model of strategic issues at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan uses a SWOT analysis approach.

Research Methodology

The subject of this research is UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, who served as the main informant in collecting information on academic and non-academic data (Gill, 2020), including the Chancellor, Head of the General Administration and Finance Bureau and Head of the Academic Bureau, and several Heads of Sections. The data collection used a guided free interview approach/technique, in this case the researcher argues that the guided interview technique besides being practical is also familiar, so that there are conveniences in obtaining data. Observation is used by researchers because data collection can be carried out directly on the object under study, besides being recorded systematically, systemically, the phenomena being investigated (Thanh et al., 2015). The purpose of using this method aims to clarify the research. And data collection is done by the method of documentation (Hamilton & Finley, 2020). Documentation is used to obtain data from documents related to the implementation of both academic and non-academic (administrative) activities at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. After the data is collected, the researcher analysis it by organizing, strengthening, processing, and classifying it systematically (McMullin, 2021). This research is a qualitative descriptive study with sentences then classified to draw conclusions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Higher Education Internationalization Issues

Referring to the National Strategy for Higher Education to 2030, there are two things that need to be a concern for universities, namely: first, regarding the formulation of an international-scale vision statement. This aims to develop institutional strategies and policies and consider international and global paradigms in a broader perspective. And second, readiness to accept foreign students (Wu, 2019). When universities are ready to accept foreign students, there should be strong support and promotion related to safety, security, and welfare for them to study and live in an area, especially in Indonesia.

The demand for studying at universities around the world is increasing, where the world is interconnected, ideas and knowledge are no longer barriers between countries (Spero, 2022). This is evidenced by lecturers, students, and researchers who have a global outlook and migration is the best opportunity, more and more students study abroad, increased institutional collaboration and collaboration, and the realization of international experiences and cultural insights between countries which are one of the core competencies. from overseas graduates.

In Indonesia, based on a source at the Bureau of Planning and Foreign Cooperation of the Ministry of Education and Culture, it is stated that the last two years (2011-2013) the number of foreign students has increased by 20%, from around 8000 foreign students to 10,000. UNESCO also noted that students currently studying in universities increased, in 2000 there were 101 million students, to 152.5 million students in 2007 and UNESCO also estimates that there are 2.8 million foreign students mobilizing to study at universities abroad. Countries

(UNESCO 2009). In Indonesia, it is also expected to increase the number of foreign students who will study in Indonesia, this is supported by government policies that collaborate between countries related to the promotion of education in Indonesia. Legally, it has been supported by the Regulation of the Minister of National Education of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2007 concerning Requirements and Procedures for Foreign Citizens to become Students at Universities in Indonesia. The internationalization of higher education is also one of the strategic policies of the Directorate of Islamic Education, namely increasing the competitiveness of Islamic universities, in order to achieve international higher education standards (Chankseliani, 2019).

Therefore, there are four key factors in conducting the internationalization of universities that must be considered, including (1) research quality; (2) teaching quality; (3) graduate employability; and (4) international outlook. Thus, universities in Indonesia can play a key role in responding to changes quickly and can use resources efficiently and effectively in order to carry out the higher education process to produce graduates who are characterized, intelligent, and skilled in advancing science and technology on an international scale. The internationalization of higher education itself is one of the ways in which a country responds to the impact of globalization, but at the same time upholds the values and culture of a nation's individuality (Troitskiy & Yun, 2021).

There are four approaches that must be considered in the internationalization of higher education, namely (1) the activity approach. This type of approach is to describe the activities of international universities, such as curriculum, student/lecturer exchange, technical assistance, and the presence of foreign students; (2) competency approach. This approach is intended to develop or respond to new skills, knowledge, attitudes and values of international standard lecturers, staff, and students; (3) the ethos approach, this approach emphasizes the creation of a higher education culture that promotes and supports international or intercultural initiatives; and (4) process approach. This approach is intended to integrate an international dimension into the teaching, research, and service processes that are combined with various activities, policies, and procedures. One of the strategies that can be done is to benchmark universities that have a world scale or universities that have received world class rankings (Edwards & Ashida, 2020).

Issues on the Implementation of Good University Governance

Implementing good governance in universities is none other than developing healthy universities, which are characterized by the functioning of organizational elements and healthy governance based on academic, ethical, and meritocratic values (Sabandar et al., 2018). The formation of an academic atmosphere that underlies the relationship between the academic community and between the academic community and stakeholders. The new paradigm of higher education encourages changes in the role and process of implementing educational institutions towards knowledge creators through strategic planning with a competitive approach (Hidayah et al., 2019). In order to carry out these roles and processes properly, the health aspect of the institution must be able to function optimally in order to realize the vision and mission it has set. The health of higher education institutions is characterized by a strong

vision and mission that is able to encourage motivation and commitment of all members of the organization, so that it has an effective and efficient structure and management, and provides a conducive working environment for all elements within the organization. Institutional capacity, programmatically and systematically must be fostered and developed, in order to be able to implement autonomy and accountability (Reschiwati et al., 2021).

Several issues that arise related to good governance include (1) organizational structure and organizational governance that are not fully in accordance with the demands of the needs and functions of services based on Minimum Service Standards (SPM); (2) the development of human resources (education and education personnel) has not been mapped and has not been based on performance; (3) the development of higher education has not been supported by ICT-based information management (information communication and technology) and the mindset of human resources has not been responsive to these technological developments; (4) the network of cooperation in the implementation of the Tri dharma of Higher Education has not been maximized; and (5) the planning and budgeting system as well as financial management information is not yet fully organized in an integrated, transparent and accountable manner (Chakim, 2019).

Universities can be able to carry out this, of course, universities are able to organize a higher education administration system that really focuses on achieving the excellence needed by the community. Referring to Nazari (2013), there are three key words to achieve the excellence that society needs, namely: quality, efficiency, and relevance. These three keywords can only be managed in a healthy management system with good university governance.

Autonomous, transparent and accountable higher education governance by prioritizing the principles of good university governance is a mandate from the National Education System Law, as stipulated in Article 48 paragraph (1) which states that the management of education funds is based on the principles of justice, efficiency, transparency and public accountability. The principle of transparency means that universities have the openness and ability to present relevant information in a timely manner in accordance with laws and regulations and applicable reporting standards to stakeholders. While the principle of accountability implies that universities have the ability and commitment to account for all activities carried out to stakeholders in accordance with statutory regulations (Selvi & Kango, 2020).

Referring to article 5, PMK Number 119/PMK.05/2007 states that the governance pattern is an internal university regulation by establishing (1) organization and management, including organizational structure, work procedures, logical grouping of functions, availability and development of human resources. , as well as cost efficiency; (2) accountability, including policies, mechanisms/procedures, media accountability and periodization of accountability for programs, activities, and finances in order to achieve the goals that have been set; and (3) transparency, by applying the principle of openness which is built on the basis of easy access to information for those who need it. Meanwhile, referring to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) it states that the indicators of success for good governance are: (1) including all; (2) transparent and accountable; (3) effective and fair; (4) guarantee the rule of law; (5)

ensure that political, social and economic priorities are based on community consensus; (6) pay attention to the weakest in decision making (Wuriyanti et al., 2020).

Higher education competition can be seen in several aspects of the following indicators:

- a. WCU rankings. Higher education competition in the industrial era 4.0 is increasingly competitive. Including global competition towards world-class universities (World Class University) which is the reference and target of various universities in various developed countries. World-class universities are universities that are able to realize their management efficiently but productively, have excellent learning quality, produce world-class graduates, produce world-quality research. Universities can be classified as world class if they have human resources who regularly publish the results of their research in the top journals in their respective disciplines and have graduates who can easily work in (countries) anywhere in the world. State Universities and Private Universities in Indonesia are vying to become a World Class University. The notion of a world class university can be understood as a ranking mechanism on an international scale. This means that there are demands in terms of operations, facilities, methods, and university graduates who are able to compete at the international level. This World Class University standard will determine the quality and quantity of a university. World Class University is a prestigious title that is worth fighting for. The reason is quite wise, namely that universities do not want to be left behind by other universities.
- b. The presence of foreign universities. Competition in universities in Indonesia is getting tougher. This is because after the government opened wide opportunities for private foreign universities to operate in Indonesia. Foreign parties are given the opportunity to establish educational institutions in Indonesia. This policy was taken not only to improve higher education services, but also concerns the era of the industrial revolution 4.0. In the implementation of higher education, foreign universities cooperate with Indonesian universities with the permission of the Minister in the fields of academics, research, and innovation for the community and industry. foreign universities hold at least 2 (two) study programs in the fields of science (science), technology (technology), engineering (engineering), and mathematics (mathematics). The curriculum organized by foreign universities is in accordance with the curriculum held in their home country and the national compulsory curriculum. This is both a threat and an opportunity. Therefore, universities in Indonesia must make improvements and innovations continuously so as not to be threatened by the presence of foreign universities (Hanum et al., 2019).

The Development and Role of Information Technology in Universities Management

The involvement of information and communication technology (ICT) in the world of education, especially in universities as higher education providers, is no longer considered an option, but has become an absolute necessity that must be utilized by universities, if they want to improve the quality of their education. World-class universities, for example Harvard University, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Stanford University, UC-Berkeley, Oxford University, Cambridge University, Univeriti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Universiti Malaya, and so

on have implemented ICT not only for educational management administration purposes, but also has been used as the main media in the implementation of teaching and learning activities, research and development, as well as services to the community. In neighboring countries, the role of ICT has been used since elementary school to university. This is the Malaysian government's commitment to developing technology literate people and even the Malaysian economy is driven by the ability to use ICT, which is known as the value-based knowledge economic concept (Nguyen & Chung, 2020).

The strategic roles of ICT in universities include: ICT as a transaction and interaction generator. ICT can be used as an enabler that allows universities to create a cheaper-better-faster education service process; ICT as an innovation in the teaching and learning process; and ICT as a performance information dashboard (Vilarinho-Pereira & Fleith, 2021).

Meanwhile, the strategic roles and responsibilities of higher education institutions must utilize ICT with the support of professional ICT management, including: Increasing community e-literacy. The task of higher education is to improve the information literacy of the community. The term information literacy is often associated with information competence, namely one's ability to utilize the information obtained to help improve one's performance; reduce the impact of the digital gap. As a developing country is the problem of the digital gap. In the context of today's world economy, what is called a digital economy and digital organization has occurred. The digital economy is a term in the economic system in a post-industrial society, namely an economy based on science, innovation economy, on-line economy, new economy, e/i-economy or the digital economy itself. Digital organization is an organization (college) that uses a computer network electronically that is connected to all internal parts of the organization through an intranet network and all stakeholders via the internet or extranet; and Generating National Competitiveness. ICT is considered to have a characteristic that is different from other technologies because almost all aspects of life and industrial sectors can apply it and derive significant benefits from ICT. Currently, various systems have developed, such as e-commerce, e-business, e-government, e-procurement, electronic data interchange, data warehouses, and so on. In the context of higher education, various terms appear, for example e-education, e-learning, virtual class, distance-learning, knowledge portal, e-library, cyber mixed/digital campus, e-student, and so on (Vasilev et al., 2020).

Technologically, referring to IEEE ComSoc Technology News, there were 10 ICT trends in 2015, including (1) 5G Mobile System; (2) Fiber Everywhere; (3) Virtualization, SDN & NFV; (4) Everywhere Connectivity for IoT & IoE; (5) Cognitive Networks, Big Data; (6) Cybersecurity; (7) Green Communications; (8) Smarter Smartphones, Connected Sensors; (9) Network Neutrality, Internet Governance; and (9) Molecular Communications. Computer networks are ubiquitous, in various forms (desktops, laptops, mobile phones, tablets, ebook readers, etc.) with formats embedded in devices, objects, and systems such as, for example, cameras, washing machines, televisions, cars, heating systems, robots, traffic control systems (Kang et al., 2021). This software is usually available in several human languages. Global standardization efforts such as Unicode solve the problem of representing and displaying different letters and special characters. Ways of interacting with computers are no longer

limited to graphical interfaces and keyboards, but are being extended through touch screens, voice interfaces and dialogue systems, and mobile devices with accelerometers that tell how the device is held by the user. Meanwhile, the development of the internet continues to grow with prices that continue to adjust to the level of capacity, cheaper than the same capacity (Novikova et al., 2020). The Ministry of Information and Communication released, in 2015 the internet network will be evenly distributed to all corners of Indonesia, with the support of very high and responsive internet providers.

New Paradigm of Issues Strategic Management at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan: SWOT Analysis

As a further elaboration of Good University Governance, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan enforces a management system with a pattern of division of authority both vertically and horizontally. Management of academic administration, development of learning resources, improvement of academic qualifications of lecturers, improvement of quality and quantity of research activities, scientific publications and community service, development of human resources, improvement of facilities and infrastructure, development of student activities, empowerment of alumni are the responsibility of the institute whose realization is controlled by the vice chancellors with the support of the Head of Bureau, Head of the institution and the Head of the Integrated Service Unit and the Dean. Meanwhile, curriculum development, learning activities, practicum, monitoring and assessment systems are the full authority of the Department/study program under the supervision of the Vice chancellor for academic and institutional development (Maulana & Adinugraha, 2020). To run it all, a system of governance that is credible, accountable, fair, transparent, and responsible as well as leadership that is operational, organizational and able to work well with all organs in UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan.

To ensure the running of the governance system of leadership and good cooperation among all within the UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan then made documents that regulate the quality assurance system. To ensure the running of the quality assurance system in every organ, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has implemented an Internal Quality Audit in the field of academic services and an internal control unit for audits in the financial sector (Nugroho et al., 2020). In addition, the availability of academic and non-academic policies as outlined in writing as clear guidelines, equipped with information technology that is used to organize academic and non-academic information in an information system. The information system is packaged in a variety of reliable and tested applications.

Referring to the achievements of key performance indicators in order to achieve the vision set by UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan as stated in the strategic plan and taking into account the internal objective conditions, it is possible to identify the strengths and weaknesses of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, both aspects: the field of institutional capability and cooperation; quality of education services; the quality of students and graduates; human Resources; finance, facilities and infrastructure; research, Community Service, and publications; data and information systems; religious moderation; gender mainstreaming; and

the environment. The strategies for each strategic policy direction are presented in the following table.

Table 1. Strategic Determination of Achievement of Key Performance Indicators based on SWOT Analysis

No	Strategic Policy Direction	Strategic Initiative Achievement Key Performance Indicators
1.	Improved access, quality and relevance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish cooperation and benchmarking with international accreditation institutions 2. Strengthening the management of Internal Quality Assurance System documents, Study Program Performance Reports and Self-Evaluation Reports 3. Socialization of Government Recognized International Certification/Accreditation Agencies 4. Intensive Study Program Accreditation Assistance 5. Implementing 9001:2015, ISO 21001:2018
2.	Capacity building and institutional competitiveness	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve managerial and leadership skills of leaders 2. Implementing the vision and mission of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan 3. Initiating international class 4. Establish cooperation with partners to increase quality capacity and institutional competitiveness
3.	Capacity building of human resources and infrastructure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assistance in the career path of lecturers and staff 2. Establish cooperation with stakeholders and alumni 3. Improving lecturer education up to doctoral level 4. Improve IT infrastructure 5. Website and social media optimization at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan
4.	Development of the tri dharma of higher education based on harmonization of knowledge	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased research and service capacity 2. Strengthening funds through research and service collaboration 3. Stimulate awards for scientific publications 4. Improving research collaboration between fellow lecturers as well as lecturers and students

Source: Documentation of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, 2022.

SWOT Analysis is based on the results of the identification of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. To obtain a strategy for achieving key performance indicators, a SWOT analysis is carried out for each strategic policy direction.

SWOT analysis on the management of strategic issues at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can be described as follows:

a. Strengths

Changes in the institutional form of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan became UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan allows UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan carried out the development of faculties and departments. This will accommodate the universal Islamic concept, namely the integration and synthesis of Islamic sciences with general sciences.

Changes in institutional status supported by a good management system that has been running provide strength from and for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to continue to develop to realize UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan became a World Class University. The following describes the analysis of the strength of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to make this happen.

Faculty and Department/Study Program Development: UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will have faculties and multidisciplinary study programs, Changes form to UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will increase the interest in accepting new students, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will accommodate the concept of universal Islam, which is able to realize the integration and synthesis of Islamic sciences (religion) with general sciences (science). Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to develop science and obtain research grants, the direction of the development of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is not only oriented towards the formation of students/graduates who have strength in the field of religious sciences, but also has professional maturity in modern science, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will have a study program that is accredited with Excellent and Excellent, considering that currently, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan already has 4 study programs accredited A, and 11 study programs accredited B, and shows an increasing trend of accreditation in recent years, Loyalty and integrity of human resources at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will be a force in competing with other universities.

Development of Scientific Integration-Based Religious Studies Program: Each faculty will provide training for lecturers of religious subjects to be able to integrate taught religious science courses with science and technology. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan produces graduates of religious experts or Muslim scholars who are knowledgeable in science and technology (Musthofiyah et al., 2021).

Development of Islamic Science-Based General Study Programs: Each faculty will provide training for general course lecturers to be able to integrate Islamic sciences into the courses they teach. By linking each course with the spirit and messages of Islam, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will produce graduates who have two advantages, namely excellence in the fields of science and technology as well as excellence in the field of Islamic insight.

Management System at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. Academic Quality Management: UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has met the standards and obtained ISO certification; UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will have a study program that is accredited with Excellent and Excellent, considering that currently, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has 4 study programs accredited A, and 11 accredited B, and shows a trend of increasing accreditation in recent years; Change of form to UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will increase the interest of new student admissions, so that it will increase the tightness of the ratio of registrants and accepted students so as to improve the quality of the inputs received; An external audit system that has been running effectively prior to the change in form through measurement criteria and assessment instruments will be maintained and

developed; Implementation of the quality assurance system at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan includes: (a) Quality Statement, (b) Quality Policy, (c) Implementing Unit, (d) Quality Standards, (e) Quality Procedures, (f) Work Instructions, (g) Phased Quality Goals, which have been integrated in a document system, and will be carried out in all work units and properly socialized and followed up; Study program development system which includes: (a) study program development, (b) preparation of accreditation documents in the form of training, funds, and information that is already owned by UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will continue to be maintained and developed after changing its form to UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan; UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will have a complete database that includes information on nine accreditation criteria for the preparation of self-evaluation documents for institutions and study programs, and can be accessed easily which is the development of a database that has been owned since before changing its form; UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will have various accredited and indexed journals, considering that currently UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has 7 Sinta 2 accredited journals, 1 Sinta 3 journal, and 1 Sinta 4 journal; There is guidance for lecturers in UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan which is held periodically related to the tri dharma of higher education and scientific integration; The existence of periodic and continuous coaching of educational staff to improve the performance and services of education personnel.

Facilities and Infrastructure Management: UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will have adequate lecture facilities and infrastructure considering that he currently has representative lecture facilities and infrastructure, and still has a large area for development; Own campus land which is classified as large and located in a strategic location, with an area of 176,124 m²; Currently, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan already has various laboratories and supporting lectures, such as microteaching laboratories, computer laboratories, language laboratories, mini bank laboratories, and so on. Therefore, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will have a very complete lecture support laboratory and support lectures.

Human Resource Management: UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will have 960 lecturers with Doctoral and Masters qualifications; The potential for adding professors at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is very large; The qualifications of the education staff are very good (some of them have qualified for Doctoral and Magister); Planning and management of human resources at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will be implemented with reference to strategic planning and job analysis; The recruitment and selection process for lecturers and education staff who have used very complete standards and refers to the Strategic Plan will continue to be maintained and improved; By becoming a UIN, it is possible for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to increase revenue and budget management for the welfare of employees, so that it will improve the competence and performance of educators and education staff at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan; Having lecturers who are mostly young workers who have the potential to continue to develop, have doctoral and postgraduate qualifications and some of them are still studying doctoral degrees; There is guidance for lecturers in UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan which is held periodically related to the tri dharma of higher education and scientific integration; The

existence of periodic and continuous coaching of educational staff to improve the performance and services of education personnel.

Institutional Management: In the organizational structure, the administration of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will have 20 organs and fulfill 5 pillars: credible, transparent, accountable, responsible, fair. The implementation of the civil service will run effectively and refer to documents and codes of ethics as well as SOPs that are clearly and completely prepared; **Leadership** at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will cover 3 characteristics, namely operational, organizational, and public and have been carried out effectively using a functional and operational management system that includes 5 functions: planning, organizing, staffing, leading, and controlling; **Operational management** at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will be implemented through 4 guidelines: (a) job design and analysis, (b) job descriptions, (c) work procedures, (d) systematic and disseminated managerial competency improvement programs and disseminated regularly to all stakeholders so that operational management it will run effectively; The external audit system that has been implemented through the measurement of criteria and assessment instruments will be maintained and improved; **Implementation of the quality assurance system** that will be carried out at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan includes: (a) Quality Statement, (b) Quality Policy, (c) Implementing Unit, (d) Quality Standards, (e) Quality Procedures, (f) Work Instructions, (g) Phased Quality Goals, which have been integrated in a document system, and carried out in all work units and proven in the form of monitoring and evaluation reports, documented, socialized and followed up properly; The study program development system that has been running at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, will be developed at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan includes: (a) development of study programs, (b) preparation of accreditation documents in the form of training, funds, and information.

Financing Management: By involving SPI and the administrative division, it will ensure budget management at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will be carried out in an accountable manner, from planning to reporting; By using the strategic plan as a reference, the use of the budget at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will be more focused and measurable; By carrying out periodic monitoring and evaluation (quarterly, semester and yearly) it is possible to know the progress of the use of the budget and the problems encountered so that the use of the budget can be carried out in a more accountable, directed, and measurable manner.

b. Weaknesses

UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is committed to always improving the quality, quality and relevance of its services in the midst of the challenges and changes of a fast-paced and competitive era. Various efforts will be taken by UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan so that various achievements will be successfully obtained as planned.

UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan must be able to overcome weaknesses in order to realize the vision and goals that have been planned. The increasing interest in new student admissions as an implication of the development of faculties and departments provides a

difficult task for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to equip students with public school backgrounds who do not yet have qualified religious abilities in the midst of community demands such as graduates of State Islamic religious colleges who are expected to have high religious abilities. This change in institutional form also has an impact on the need to increase human resources both in terms of quantity and quality which are currently insufficient. If these weaknesses can be overcome properly, an optimal management system will be realized in order to achieve the vision and goals of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan.

The following describes the results of the analysis of the weaknesses that can appear at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan.

Faculty and Department/Study Program Development: The diversity of majors at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan made this campus not only in demand by graduates of religious schools, but also graduates of public schools. As a result, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan because students with public school backgrounds are potential, but do not yet have qualified religious abilities, while the demands of society such as graduates of State Islamic religious universities are expected to have high religious abilities; Development of faculties and study programs at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has implications for the need for additional human resources which are currently not sufficient; Less than optimal analysis of community needs related to the opening of new study programs; The development of faculties and study programs is directly proportional to the development of campus management which may not be ready to be faced by all human resources owned; This development has implications for the need for adequate facilities and infrastructure.

Development of Scientific Integration-Based Religious Studies Programs: The development of scientific integration-based religious studies programs makes the burden of student credits become large which will have implications for the difficulty of students to graduate in less than four years; The integration of religious knowledge based on scientific integration has implications for the reduced focus of students in the field of science they are engaged in.

Development of General Study Programs Based on Islamic Sciences: The development of general study programs based on Islamic sciences makes the burden of student credits become large which will have implications for the difficulty of students to graduate in less than four years; The integration of general sciences based on general sciences has implications for the reduced focus of students in the field of science they are engaged in.

Management System at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. Academic Quality Management: The diversity of majors at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan made this campus not only in demand by graduates of religious schools, but also graduates of public schools. As a result, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan because students with public school backgrounds do not yet have qualified religious abilities, while the demands of the people who graduate from State Islamic religious universities are like having high religious abilities; Although UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan developed a quality assurance system that already existed at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, but it is possible

that the implementation of his work program has not been maximized; IT-based administrative management raises its own problems due to continuous data updating.

Facilities and Infrastructure Management: Asset management is not optimal. It is still necessary to optimize the provision of supporting facilities and infrastructure. The location of campus 1 and campus 2 are far enough apart so that it requires more personnel to maintain facilities and infrastructure of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, In completing the facilities and infrastructure, rules and regulations are sometimes hampered, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is a government institution so that the selection of locations for development must be in accordance with the location determination by the Governor, including the committee must involve relevant agencies.

Human Resource Management: The potential for tight recruitment of lecturers and education staff has not been achieved, with the general study program at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, it opens up more opportunities for recruited lecturers who do not have adequate basic religious knowledge so that coaching is still needed.

Institutional Management: With the addition of organs at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, still has to be accompanied by the addition of the availability of human resources which are currently still classified as inadequate, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will manage the main tasks and functions of human resources at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. However, the current competencies of each are different and do not meet the ideal qualifications, so they still require additional formations that can be done gradually. Human resources currently have carried out their duties based on authority and responsibility as well as job descriptions, it will be maintained. However, there are still human resources who lack time discipline, so they tend to rely on each other and do not support the performance of the institution optimally. There are still some employees who have not been able to adjust to the change in status to UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, so that sometimes it becomes an obstacle to achieving the goals of the institution.

Financing Management: It is still not optimal to extract funds outside the State Budget, by transforming into UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has implications for the addition of faculties, units, and institutions, so there needs to be an increase in discipline and control over planning, implementing, and reporting activities at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan.

c. Opportunities

By becoming UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan increasingly opens up opportunities to continue to grow and contribute. UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can take opportunities, and develop new innovations.

UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can also contribute more optimally to solve problems that arise in society from various scientific angles. The following opportunities will be obtained by UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan and strived to be utilized properly by the academic community.

Development of Faculties and Departments/Study Programs: The rapid development of the Pekalongan region from an economic perspective has made graduates of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will not only be absorbed in educational or religious institutions, but also in institutions engaged in economics, business, law, and others. This will open up more opportunities for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to obtain scholarship offers and internships for students from these institutions and agencies, as has been done by Bank Indonesia, Baznas, Mizan Printing, Pekalongan Regency Government, PT Pelindo III, BNI Bank, and the Indonesian Human Capital Forum, In this competitive era, the community not only expects the competence of higher education graduates who have the competence, expertise, science and technology, as well as the skills needed to achieve a decent and prosperous life, they also realize the importance of a solid provision of religious knowledge, to equip graduates to become strong individuals. Uphold ethics, morals, noble character, and good deeds. This, becomes very relevant by becoming a UIN, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, in which there is no longer a scientific dichotomy, makes it possible to produce graduate competencies as expected by the community, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can contribute to the preparation of superior and professional human resources, as well as having good character, and being able to compete in the national and international arena, Increasing the learning awareness index of the Pekalongan community to continue their education to the tertiary level, Limited public universities in the former Pekalongan Residency area , There are many Islamic educational institutions, both madrasas and Islamic boarding schools in the former Pekalongan Residency area, Starting to increase cooperation with strategic partners from the government, private sector, and other universities, both from within and outside the country, There is support from the central and regional governments, and other stakeholders to accelerate the development of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan became UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, By becoming a UIN, gave UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to seek opportunities, take roles, and develop new innovations that were previously inaccessible, Able to solve problems that arise in society from various scientific angles.

Development of Religious Studies Program Based on Scientific Integration. The rapid development of the Pekalongan region from an economic perspective has made UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will not only be absorbed in educational or religious institutions, but also in institutions engaged in economics, business, law, and others. This will open up more opportunities for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to get scholarship offers and internships for students from these institutions and agencies, as has been done by Bank Indonesia, Baznas, Mizan Printing, Pekalongan Regency Government, PT Pelindo III, BNI Bank, and the Indonesian Human Capital Forum.

Development of Islamic Studies-Based General Study Programs: In this competitive era, the community not only expects the competence of university graduates who have the competencies, expertise, science and technology, as well as the skills needed to achieve a decent and prosperous life, they also realize the importance of the provision of knowledge. a solid religion, to equip graduates to become individuals who uphold ethics, morals, noble character, and good deeds. UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, in which there is no

longer a scientific dichotomy, making it possible to produce graduate competencies as expected by society; UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can contribute to the preparation of superior and professional human resources, with good character, and able to compete in the national and international arena.

The management system of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. Academic Quality Management: The rapid development of the Pekalongan region from an economic perspective has made UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan will not only be absorbed in educational or religious institutions, but also in institutions engaged in economics, business, law, and others. This will open up more opportunities for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to obtain scholarship offers and internships for students from these institutions and agencies, as has been done by Bank Indonesia, Baznas, Mizan Printing, Pekalongan Regency Government, PT Pelindo III, BNI Bank, and the Indonesian Human Capital Forum, In this competitive era, the community not only expects the competence of higher education graduates who have the competence, expertise, science and technology, as well as the skills needed to achieve a decent and prosperous life, they also realize the importance of a solid provision of religious knowledge, to equip graduates to become strong individuals. Uphold ethics, morals, noble character, and good deeds. This, becomes very relevant by becoming a UIN, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, in which there is no longer a scientific dichotomy, makes it possible to produce graduate competencies as expected by the community, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can contribute to the preparation of superior and professional human resources, and has good morals, and is able to compete in the national and international arena, Limited public universities in the former Pekalongan Residency area, There are many Islamic educational institutions both madrasas and Islamic boarding schools in the former Pekalongan area. Pekalongan Residency, starting to increase cooperation with strategic partners from the government, private sector, and other universities, both from within and outside the country, The declaration of 2025 as a time when universities in Indonesia can speak at the world level by the Ministry of Education and Culture opens opportunities for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to take part in the contestation of academic and scientific activities in the world.

Management of Facilities and Infrastructure: By changing its form to UIN, it opens up opportunities for stakeholders and related agencies to provide support for facilities and infrastructure. By becoming a university, it opens up opportunities for collaboration with various related agencies to provide assistance for lecture infrastructure, Development of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan opened up opportunities to get grants to develop UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan.

Human Resource Management: Opportunities given by the Ministry of Religion to UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to submit a proposal for the procurement of permanent lecturers and permanent education staff, both civil servants and non-civil servants every year. The national recruitment system for lecturers and education staff has the opportunity for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan attracts as many interested people as possible with the best quality, External Audit Implementation held at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid

Pekalongan has the opportunity to improve the performance of lecturers and education staff, permanent lecturers have many opportunities to take part outside UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, because he has excellent competence according to the needs of outsiders.

Institutional Management: An effective leadership culture characterized by a quality assurance system with internal quality audits carried out on an ongoing basis, opening up opportunities for improving the quality of education and enabling national and international recognition as a leading and competitive Islamic religious university. high level in policy making and program implementation, opening opportunities for development towards wider interests of the academic community in various aspects, Good achievements in the Strategic Management System which have been embraced open opportunities for collaboration from relevant agencies and Islamic religious universities throughout Indonesia for institutional development, the ISO certificate that has been obtained opens up opportunities for collaboration with other institutions or universities, both at home and abroad. **Financing Management.** By changing the form to UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan can have implications for increasing the number of students so that it can increase Non-Tax State Revenue, the Status of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan becoming a BLU can increase revenue. By becoming a university, it will increase the opportunities for collaboration with other parties, such as associations, banks and government/private institutions that can increase the university's income. Functioned as a meeting building, hotel, or other after renovation and adjustment, in addition to SBSN funds, there is still the possibility to access funds from IDB for campus development, Pekalongan district government's attention is quite large on the development of universities, opening opportunities for cooperation and financial support in the development of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan.

d. Threats

Development to become UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is not without threats. Especially at this time, the index of learning awareness in Pekalongan is increasing, triggering the growth in the number of universities in the Pekalongan area. In addition, the more pragmatic society that emphasizes job opportunities (market oriented) is a challenge that must be faced by UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan.

The following presents the results of the threat analysis that will be faced by UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. By reducing existing weaknesses and optimizing strengths and opportunities, threats that arise will be faced and overcome properly.

Development of Faculties and Departments/Study Programs: The presence of new universities in the Pekalongan area increases competition in the recruitment of new students, Pekalongan's condition is still minimal from several aspects compared to Semarang, making prospective students less likely because they prefer other State Islamic religious universities such as UIN Semarang, supported by the National Academic Achievement Selection online achievement recruitment system which makes it easier for prospective students in the registration process, The lifestyle of modern society which has a high demand for multi-competent worker's demands UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to equip graduates with a variety of extra

competencies, not limited to competencies that are directly related to majors, The current era developments have caused changes in people's orientation towards education which increasingly emphasizes job opportunities (market oriented), Job qualifications currently demand quality resources high human resources, strengthening demands for higher education policies and autonomy and transparent, accountable, and competitive governance, so that UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is required to be more professional in managing the institution, As the development of information and communication technology demands the availability of qualified human resources, the institutional transformation into a UIN has had an effect on the demands of the community who crave quality Islamic educational institutions in terms of service and output and are affordable from the financing side.

Development of Religious Studies Program Based on Scientific Integration. There are still many people who look down on graduates from state Islamic religious universities. Development of General Studies Program Based on Islamic Sciences. There are still many institutions, companies, or agencies that look down on graduates from state Islamic religious universities.

Management System at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. Academic Quality Management: The increasing public criticism along with the expansion of access to information has made their control power tighter, thus demanding UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan improves accountability and transparency both in recruiting new students, fostering students, as well as in organizing extracurricular activities. The lifestyle of modern society which has a high demand for multi-competent worker's demands that UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to equip graduates with a variety of extra competencies, not limited to competencies that are directly related to majors, The current era developments have led to changes in people's orientation towards education which increasingly emphasizes job opportunities (market oriented), Job qualifications currently demand quality human resources high demands, strengthening demands for higher education policies and autonomy and governance that are transparent, accountable, and competitive, so that UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is required to be more professional in managing the institution. As the development of information and communication technology demands the availability of qualified human resources, the institutional transformation into UIN has had an effect on the demands of the community who crave quality Islamic educational institutions in terms of service and output and affordable in terms of financing, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has to compete with other universities that have a vision to become a world-class university. Facilities and Infrastructure Management: UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan was challenged by other universities that were earlier established and had more complete facilities and infrastructure. Human Resource Management: The quota-based lecturer certification process hinders the acceleration of lecturer certification at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan must compete with other universities, especially PTU, in recruiting lecturers to get general course lecturers with the best qualifications. Institutional Management: UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan needs to continuously improve the managerial system in order to adapt to other universities that have already transformed. The potential for institutional inaccuracies in analyzing the needs and

interests of the community in the opening of new Study Programs can cause Study Programs to be empty of enthusiasts. Financing Management: Increasingly tight budgeting and financial reporting systems cause vulnerability to audit findings conducted by external parties (Audit Board of the Republic of Indonesia and Inspectorate General of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia), Increased public criticism along with widespread access to information, making their control power more stringent, thus demanding UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan increases accountability and transparency in the use and management of finances. The low purchasing power of the people causes low public participation in the education budget. In detail SWOT Analysis as presented in the following figures:

Figure. 1: Improved access, quality and relevance

Figure. 2: Capacity building and institutional competitiveness

Figure. 3: Capacity building of human resources and infrastructure

Figure. 4: Development of the tri dharma of higher education based on harmonization of knowledge

Based on strategic issues and external environmental conditions, it can be concluded that every organization generally faces strategic environmental problems, both internal and external. The internal environment is an environmental factor that affects organizational performance which can usually be controlled directly, while the external environment is an environmental factor that affects organizational performance which is beyond the control of the organization but greatly affects the activities of the organization. UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan as one of the state Islamic religious higher education organizations in Indonesia which is growing rapidly because UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is the only public university in Pekalongan Regency. The total number of universities in Pekalongan Regency is still relatively small. This proves that UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan

has the potential to be developed further. One of the strategies that can be used is to determine a stable growth strategy, meaning that in competition in the field of education, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan uses a role growth strategy but is carried out in stages according to a priority scale.

For example, to become a World Class University (WCU), UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan requires managerial readiness and a stable growth strategy that must be developed by State Islamic religious universities with a planned, programmed, directed, systemic character. Some of the WCU assessment institutions have several indicators and different assessment characters, but in general the assessments of several WCU assessing institutions prioritize the quantity and quality of research, outputs from universities that are reliable and ready to compete in the world of work, the number of lecturers and student's international affairs, the effectiveness of higher education webs and the implementation of good university governance. To achieve the reputation of WCU, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan has determined strategic steps that must be carried out, namely increasing the quantity and quality of research results at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan published, providing quality teaching services and in accordance with the needs of stakeholders, website development at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, leadership at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, implementation of good university governance at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, alliance and network of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan with other institutions, the internationalization of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, application of higher education culture at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. Reliable planning, supporting higher education facilities and infrastructure are not one of the supporting factors for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to achieve the reputation of WCU. Input and support from UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan as well as organizational commitment from lecturers, staff and students, are the most important factors for UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan to reach a university that has international qualifications. Management of strategic issues at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid has long been the aspiration of the entire academic community, so in recent years a systematic effort to realize his strategy is based on the SWOT analysis described above. The management of strategic issues based on a SWOT analysis is certainly not because of following trends alone, but rather because of a substantive rationale. The rationale includes philosophical, academic, sociological, juridical and historical foundations.

Philosophically, the management of strategic issues at UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is intended to improve the quality of science that is more integrative and to prepare future generations of the nation who excel in faith, piety, and science and technology. Academically, the management of this strategic issue provides opportunities for the development of new faculties and study programs which have implications for increasing student capacity. Sociologically, the management of strategic issues allows prospective graduates to enter the world of work and a wider field of service and can solve problems in an increasingly complex society. Juridically, managing this strategic issue means fulfilling the calls and regulations of the government as a higher education institution that is quite experienced, well-established and able to compete with other universities, especially in

Indonesia. The purpose of managing strategic issues based on this SWOT analysis is to answer the constitutional mandate, which is to be actively involved in the intellectual life of the nation, develop life skills and abilities, and improve the quality of life and human dignity of Indonesia in an effort to realize national goals. In this case, the management of strategic issues based on a SWOT analysis is related to the development of an integralistic and comprehensive education system in various disciplines in order to produce professional and moral intellectuals. This try hard can present more diverse disciplines, perspectives, approaches and scientific orientations. This diversity will then be able to bring an attitude of tolerance and mutual respect.

CONCLUSSION

The results of this study found that the SWOT analysis of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan in the management of strategic issues is made based on four components, namely the needs of the community, the needs of national development, the development of science and technology and the arts, as well as the potential for growth in the number of students. From the analysis of these needs, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is required to prepare graduates who have work skills, prepare graduates who have the ability to adapt, prepare graduates who have a creative mindset, increase equitable access to higher education, improve higher education quality, increase the relevance and competitiveness of higher education, strengthen higher education autonomy. , strengthen the spread of religious messages, and strengthen religious moderation and multicultural spirit. The direction of the development strategy of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan is carried out based on three stages, namely short term (good university governance), medium term (competitive advantage university) and long term (global recognition university). In the short-term stage, development is directed at strengthening governance, improving institutional performance and developing a scientific base with an Indonesian perspective. In the medium terms stage, development is directed at increasing access, quality, competitiveness and scientific contributions with an Indonesian perspective at the national level. In the long-term stage, development is directed at international engagement as a leading Islamic religious university in the management of institutions and the development of science and technology with a national and global perspective.

The findings of this study also show that external factors are positive but internal factors are negative. This position shows that the opportunities faced are still greater than the existing threats. On the internal side, the strengths or advantages they have are relatively smaller than their weaknesses. Thus, the policy direction that must be chosen is to maintain the role of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan that has existed and is currently ongoing aggressively or selectively in carrying out work programs that are indeed possible. In this condition, the basic policy direction that must be implemented is to maintain stability towards existing and ongoing activities.

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